

The fluctuation of incidence on control Ambalalava reflects the year-to-year climatic variation; the lower the temperatures, the higher the incidence (Fig. 1). The incidence on bulk populations was very high and did not change between 1988 and 1989, although yield loss decreased from 55 to 25%, which was the level of the control. Natural selection eliminated the individuals that

showed a high severity in 1988 (Fig. 2).

In 1990, no incidences or losses occurred on Ambalalava. The incidence in the hybrids stayed at the same level as Ambalalava in the preceding year, but with only 4% of the losses (Fig. 1). Incidence increased 10% for the hybrids the following year, resulting in increased losses of 8% for Ambalalava and 22% for the hybrid families.

The differences of scale between the two groups are due to the *sd₁* gene. It has a critical threshold of incidence that leads to losses of 30-40% in modern varieties. Good panicle exertion is needed to lessen BSR losses. We are using IR50, which has the *eui* (elongated uppermost internode) gene, in our breeding program to obtain modern varieties that are more resistant to BSR. ■

IRGC 100139, an accession of *Oryza glaberrima* sensitive to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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RTSV is a latent virus of rice. About 1,200 rice accessions have been tested at IRRI for RTSV, but none of them were sensitive enough to show distinct symptoms of RTSV infection.

We tested four accessions of *O. glaberrima* for sensitivity to RTSV by

inoculating 7-d-old seedlings with one adult green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant)/plant for 24 h in a test tube. The infected plants showed marked stunting, reduced tillering, and pale green leaves at 3-4 wk after inoculation (see figure). Flowering was delayed and panicles were short with few, small grains. Inoculation infected 80-90% of plants.

IRGC 100139 is the first rice accession of *O. glaberrima* identified at IRRI that consistently showed distinct symptoms when infected with RTSV. IRGC 100139 is also a good virus source. When adult GLH had 3 d access to RTSV-infected IRGC 100139 plants,

more than 80% of the insects transmitted the virus to either TN1 or IRGC 100139. The results indicate that RTSV can be maintained and propagated in IRGC 100139.

At present, RTSV is detected in plants by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay or by latex test. These tests are expensive and are not available in most laboratories in developing countries. The tests could be eliminated by using IRGC 100139 as an indicator plant for RTSV. The accession can be used to monitor RTSV-carrying leafhoppers caught in the field and for survey of RTSV occurrence in regions where no tungro symptoms are visible. ■

Healthy (left) and RTSV-infected (right) *O. glaberrima* plants at 21 d after inoculation.

Resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) in rice germplasm

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We used the mass screening test to determine resistance to rice tungro disease (RTD) of about 16,000 accessions of the International Rice Germplasm Center (IRGC). We selected 510 accessions that showed resistance to RTD and tested for resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) using forced inoculation in test tubes and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Plants were inoculated by confining a 6-d-old seedling with three viruliferous green leafhoppers (GLH) in a test tube for 24 h. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted into pots and grown in a greenhouse. Serological indexing was carried out 30 d after inoculation by taking 10-cm-long pieces from the 2d or

3d youngest leaf of each of the 40 plants/ accession.

When inoculated with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and RTSV, only one accession showed a RTBV infection rate of less than 10%, while 251 accessions (49%) showed a RTSV infection rate below 10%; 147 accessions (29%) were not infected with RTSV.

We further evaluated 134 accessions with RTSV-infection rate below 10% by inoculating them with RTSV alone to confirm their resistance. Results revealed that 115 accessions (86%) had an RTSV infection rate below 10%. Seventy-six accessions were not infected with RTSV in the two experiments (see table on next page).

These results indicate that many varieties are available to serve as sources of resistance to RTSV. Some accessions that had low RTSV infection rates in both experiments and GLH resistance (resistance score <5) were omitted from the table because they may show RTSV resistance caused by vector resistance. ■